

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED AND COPING STRATEGIES APPLIED BY THE STAKEHOLDERS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES AFTER THE PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the challenges encountered and coping strategies applied by internal and external stakeholders during the implementation of face-to-face classes after a pandemic. Employing a quantitative-descriptive design, the research relied on a survey questionnaire as its primary data collection tool. Participants encompassed both internal stakeholders (comprising learners, teachers, and school personnel) and external stakeholders (including parents or guardian, local government officials (LGU), and barangay officials) from Atimonan Districts I and II, selected through random sampling. The study's primary objectives included identifying the challenges confronted during the reintroduction of in-person classes and understanding the coping strategies employed by stakeholders. Additionally, it sought to assess whether significant differences existed in the challenges and coping strategies applied by internal and external stakeholders within Atimonan Districts. The study revealed that the challenges encountered by the internal stakeholders include concerns about health and safety, adapting to new protocols, and managing classroom dynamics. In contrast, external stakeholders faced difficulties related to resource allocation, effective communication, and garnering community support for the reopening of schools. Meanwhile, Internal stakeholders devised coping strategies such as rigorous training in health and safety protocols, collaborative lesson planning, and adjusting teaching methods to accommodate new classroom dynamics. External stakeholders employed strategies like mobilizing resources, establishing efficient communication channels, and fostering

community involvement to address the identified challenges. The study uncovered significant differences in the challenges applied by internal and external stakeholders in implementing in-person classes, suggesting that the nature of challenges varied between these two groups. However, no significant differences were found in the coping strategies employed by both internal and external stakeholders, indicating a level of alignment in their approaches to overcome challenges. Based on these findings, several recommendations emerge develop comprehensive plans that prioritize safety and well-being while considering various scenarios. Invest in professional development for teachers to enhance their skills in blended learning and technology integration. Involve teachers, parents, and students in decision-making processes to ensure inclusiveness. Prioritize the health and safety of students and staff by adhering to recommended protocols. Be flexible in teaching methods to address varying student needs. Identify and address learning gaps that may have arise during remote learning. Maintain open communication with teachers and school administrators to address concerns and provide support for their learners. Offer emotional support to help learners navigate the challenges of returning to face-to-face classes. Conduct further research to analyze the short-term and long-term effects of the pandemic on education systems, learners, teachers, and parents. Identify best practices and areas for improvement in handling future crises in education.

Keywords: *Challenges Encountered, Internal Stakeholders, External Stakeholders, Coping Strategies, Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan*

INTRODUCTION

Face-to-face Education is the most conventional kind of Education. It is the most popular instructional approach in which learning materials are presented in person, one-on-one, or, more typically, to a group of students in a closed classroom (Fernandez-Guzman et al., 2020). They allow the students to exercise and converse with ease. The face-to-face class offers benefits that modules and online Education cannot match.

Before the Pandemic, face-to-face classes represent the daily life of teachers and students going through different curricular subjects. The typical class flow starts without restrictions, and the students are free to have collaborative activities that encourage ICT integration but are mostly offline. They enjoy learning freely without the risk of having infected by a virus. Then the Pandemic arrived. The COVID-19 epidemic has caused enormous economic, social, and political concerns. In addition to a health catastrophe, it has also caused an educational crisis and lockdown. Hence, on February 9, 2020, the Department of Health (DOH) provided an evidence-based independent technical assessment on the COVID-19-related class suspension, which started the nationwide history of class suspensions and lockdown with the support of the 10th Inter-Agency Task Force. Likewise, DepEd (2020) worked on adopting the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 considering the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency through D.O. No. 12, s. 2020 uses alternative learning modalities besides face-to-face teaching, including modular distance learning, television and radio learning,

and online and blended learning modalities. Then upon the observed decreasing risk of the Corona Virus and the near 100% core immunity, DepEd seized the opportunity to reopen class with limited face-to-face modalities contained in DepEd Order No. 34, s—2022, which was Duterte's first order as education chief. The order also stated that the school year 2022 – 2023 will be on August 22 and end on July 7, 2023. Nonetheless, catastrophes and pandemics cause significant challenges and changes in educational delivery, resources, and the environment. There is evidence that the probability of pandemics has grown over the last century due to increasing global travel and integration, urbanization, changes in land use, and higher exploitation of the natural environment (Madhav et al., 2022) Such pandemics that the world experienced are the Black Death, Spanish Flue, and HIV/AIDS. According to Madhav et al. (2022), the tremendous diversity of viruses and their interactions with people drives the range of pandemic dangers. Hence, being resilient to pandemics should be one of the goals of the education sector, such as DepEd.

In addition, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, human interaction, system functioning, and resource allocation have changed. Education is compelled to utilize this new compass to navigate the world of teaching and learning while protecting the mental health of the learners (Tuccie et al., 2019) against fear or guilt Deaton (2018), deviant behavior (UNICEF, 2020) as well as family problems. Despite these evolving dynamics, meeting the educational needs of learners continues to be a priority; learners' rights to Education remain protected and non-negotiable. The ultimate objectives of Education remain the same, but the tools to achieve them must be revised and applied differently, such as the learning continuity and recovery plan (Sarmiento et al., 2021).

The situations above, setting, literature, and research testify to the necessity to examine the need to analyze the challenges encountered and coping strategies brought by implementing face-to-face lessons. No research has yet been undertaken to analyze the stakeholders' experiences conducting face-to-face teaching sessions and establish a resilient and reliable learning recovery and a continuity plan in the context of Atimonan I and II Districts in Quezon Province. This investigation was suggested.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered and coping strategies applied by internal and external stakeholders in implementing face-to-face classes after the pandemic.

Specifically, this aims to answer the following questions.

1. What are the challenges encountered by the internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic in terms of:
 - 1.1. Managing School Operations
 - 1.1.1. Shared Responsibility;
 - 1.1.2. Work Arrangements;
 - 1.1.3. Classroom Layout and Structure;
 - 1.1.4. School Traffic Management;

- 1.1.5. Protective Measures, Hygiene Practices, and Safety Procedures;
 - 1.1.6. Communication Strategy; and
 - 1.1.7. Contingency Plan?
 - 1.2. Focusing on Teaching and Learning
 - 1.2.1 Learning Resources;
 - 1.2.2 Face-to-Face Classes; and
 - 1.2.3 Teacher's Support?
 - 1.3 Well-being and Protection
 - 1.3.1 School disinfection and Sanitation;
 - 1.3.2 COVID-19 Case Management; and
 - 1.3.3 Including the most Marginalized?
 - 1.4 School-Community Coordination?
 2. What are the coping strategies applied by the internal and external stakeholders to address the challenges encountered in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic in terms of:
 - 2.1. Managing School Operations
 - 2.1.1. Shared Responsibility;
 - 2.1.2. Work Arrangements;
 - 2.1.3. Classroom Layout and Structure;
 - 2.1.4. School Traffic Management;
 - 2.1.5. Protective Measures, Hygiene Practices, and Safety Procedures;
 - 2.1.6. Communication Strategy; and
 - 2.1.7. Contingency Plan?
 - 2.2. Focusing on Teaching and Learning
 - 2.2.1. Learning Resources;
 - 2.2.2. Face-to-Face Classes; and
 - 2.2.3. Teacher's Support?
 - 2.3 Well-being and Protection
 - 2.3.1 School disinfection and Sanitation;
 - 2.3.2 COVID-19 Case Management; and
 - 2.3.3 Including the most Marginalized
 - 2.4. School-Community Coordination?
 3. Is there a significant difference on the challenges encountered by the internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic?
 4. Is there a significant difference on the coping strategies applied by the internal and external stakeholders to address the challenges encountered in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic?
 5. What School Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan can be prepared by the researcher based on the research results?
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METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, the locale of the study, the population and sampling procedures, the research instruments utilized, procedures for gathering data, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The quantitative method was utilized in this study, employing the descriptive research design (Creswell, 2013). This design collected quantifiable data for the statistical analysis of a population sample. It was used to identify the participants' qualities, including their traits, behavior, and opinions. This information could be acquired through surveys sent to the respondents and the study subjects. Descriptive research was used to determine the underlying patterns of the study item. It also used a survey type questionnaire to identify the respondents' opinions on the challenges encountered and coping strategies applied to address the challenges encountered in implementing face-to-face classes after the pandemic, which were later statistically compared.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the municipality of Atimonan in the province of Quezon. It was a first-class municipality with 64,260 residents, according to the 2020 census. It was located on the province's eastern shore, 42 kilometers (26 miles) from Lucena City and 172 kilometers (107 miles) from Manila. The towns of Gumaca, Plaridel, Pagbilao, and Padre Burgos surrounded Atimonan.

In the context of DepEd, Atimonan was divided into two (2) districts, the Atimonan I District with six (6) public secondary schools, while Atimonan II District has two (2) public secondary schools.

Figure 2. Location Map of Atimonan, Quezon

The locale was chosen as the place of the study because the researcher wanted to contribute her research findings to Atimonan I and II Districts, and this research could be used for future references in case of a similar pandemic. Second, this would greatly help her Schools Division in terms of quality instruction. Third, the researcher loved the students, parents, teachers, and school personnel of the Atimonan I and II Districts. It was her pride and honor that her research would be beneficial to all stakeholders, and that this research could contribute to her Division.

Research Population and Sample

There were 6660 total internal and external stakeholders, and the sample size calculator with a .05 margin of error was used to identify the number of sample respondents selected from the pool of stakeholders in Atimonan I and II Districts of DepEd Quezon.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by School*

Districts/ Municipality	Number of Stakeholders			Total	Number of External Stakeholders			Total	Total No. Of Respondents
	Student	Teacher	Personnel		Parent	LGU	Private Individual		
Atimonan I District									
Atimonan National Comprehensive High School	30	18	12	60	20	3	3	26	86
Balubad Integrated School	10	14	6	30	8	2	2	12	42
Caridad Integrated School	9	8	5	22	10	2	2	14	36
Malusak Integrated National High School	5	5	5	15	11	3	2	16	31
San Rafael National High School	6	3	6	15	10	2	2	14	29
Villa Ibaba Integrated School	6	9	5	20	9	2	1	12	32
Atimonan II District									
Malinao Ilaya Integrated National High School	22	14	8	44	11	3	3	17	61
Maligaya Integrated National High School	10	15	10	35	10	2	2	14	49
Grand Total	98	86	57	241	89	19	17	125	366

The internal stakeholders were composed of 241 learners, teachers, and non-teaching personnel, while there were 125 external stakeholders participating in the study, consisting of selected parents and guardians, and local government units. Given the substantial number of both internal and external stakeholders in the municipality, purposive sampling procedures were used, and the respondents were selected based on their proactive involvement in the conduct of face-to-face classes in their respective and affiliated schools.

Research Instruments

A modified researcher-made checklist questionnaire was used to collect the necessary data. The basis for this instrument was D.O. No. 30 s. of 2022, outlining guidelines for implementing face-to-face classes in the country. The questionnaire was divided into three (3) parts.

Part I aimed to identify the stakeholders' roles as internal or external. Part II was used to identify the challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in implementing face-to-face classes, specifically in managing school operations, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and school-community coordination. Part III focused on the coping strategies applied by the internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes. Four (4) point scales were employed in the research instrument for the challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders, where 4 represented the highest challenge, and 1 represented the lowest. The scale underwent validation to align with the objectives of the study. The scale values were 4 for Most Challenging, 3 for More Challenging, 2 for Moderately Challenging, and 1 for Less Challenging.

Similarly, four (4) point scales were used in the research instrument for the coping strategies applied by stakeholders, where 4 represented the highest, and 1 represented the lowest. The scale values were 4 for Most Applied, 3 for More Applied, 2 for Moderately Applied, and 1 for Less Applied.

The questionnaires underwent thorough validation with the assistance of master teachers, school heads, education program supervisors, and research experts. After incorporating the suggestions of the validators, the questionnaires were piloted for item analysis to finalize the research instrument. Subsequently, the facilitation followed.

Data Gathering Procedure

To fully achieve the research goals, the researcher drafted letters addressed to the validators of the research instrument, the schools' division superintendent, public school district supervisors, and school heads, seeking their permission to conduct the study. Additionally, a cover letter was included, outlining the purpose, value, and the necessity of responding to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of the information provided. A separate letter was sent to each participant from the chosen schools.

After confirming the SDS's approval, the researcher will commence contacting school administrators, instructors, and the local IATF regarding the study's conduct, including on-site data collection and the potential face-to-face administration of questionnaires to the selected respondents. The researcher aims to personally administer the questionnaires to ensure the veracity of the data.

Furthermore, respondents were informed about the research objectives and the components of the questionnaire. The researcher addressed any queries from the respondents to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the intent behind the inquiries.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were employed to summarize, present, analyze, and interpret the collected data: quantitative methodology and frequency count, and T-test. Weighted mean was utilized to identify the challenges encountered by the internal and external stakeholders and coping strategies applied by the internal and external stakeholders to address the challenges encountered. This focus encompassed managing

school operations, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and school-community coordination.

Finally, the T-test for independent samples applied to test hypotheses and ascertain if there is a significant difference between the challenges encountered and coping strategies applied by stakeholders in implementing face-to-face classes in the Atimonan Districts among internal and external stakeholders.

To assess the level of challenges encountered and coping strategies applied by respondents in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, a Likert Scale was used to calculate the mean.

Likert Scale on the Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders

Point	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Description
4	3.26 - 4.00	Most Challenging (MC)	The challenges encountered is most challenging equivalent to 76% to 100%.
3	2.51 - 3.25	More Challenging (MRC)	The challenges encountered is more challenging equivalent to 51% to 75%.
2	1.76 – 2.50	Moderately Challenging (MDC)	The challenges encountered is moderately challenging equivalent to 26% to 50%.
1	1.00 – 1.75	Less Challenging (LC)	The challenges encountered is most challenging equivalent to 01% to 25%.

Likert Scale on the Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders

Point	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Description
4	3.26 - 4.00	Most Applied (MA)	The coping strategies is most applied equivalent to 76% to 100%.
3	2.51 - 3.25	More Applied (MRA)	The coping strategies is more applied equivalent to 51% to 75%.
2	1.76 – 2.50	Moderately Applied (MDA)	The coping strategies is moderately applied equivalent to 26% to 50%.
1	1.00 – 1.75	Less Applied (LA)	The coping strategies is less applied equivalent to 01% to 25%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic

Table 1.1.1

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Shared Responsibility

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has no limited mobilization of resources and support from community stakeholders to meet the standards of the health and safety protocols.	2.97	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
2.The school did not conduct simulation activities among school personnel regarding protocols and routines to replicate and discuss possible scenarios during the actual conduct of face-to-face classes.	2.94	More Challenging	2.88	More Challenging
Grand Mean	2.96	More Challenging	2.89	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*

1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*

1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.1.1 shows the perceptions of both internal and external stakeholders regarding the challenges encountered both internal and external stakeholders during the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic in managing school operations in terms of shared responsibility.

The grand mean for both internal and external stakeholders is 2.96 and 2.89, respectively, indicating an overall perception of "More Challenging" conditions in implementing post-pandemic in-person classes. The standard deviations for both groups suggest moderate consistency in responses.

Indicator 1 reveals that internal stakeholders perceive challenges in mobilizing resources and support from community stakeholders to meet health and safety protocols, with a weighted mean score of 2.97. This implies that they find it challenging to secure the necessary resources and support from the community to ensure compliance with safety protocols during in-person classes.

Indicator 2 highlights that internal stakeholders perceive challenges because the school did not conduct simulation activities among school personnel regarding protocols

and routines. The weighted mean score is 2.94, indicating that internal stakeholders find the absence of preparatory simulation activities challenging in preparing for in-person classes.

External stakeholders, as indicated in Indicator 1, also find it challenging to mobilize resources and support from the community to meet health and safety protocols, with a weighted mean score of 2.90. This suggests that external stakeholders share a similar perception of limited support from the community in ensuring a safe learning environment.

Indicator 2 shows that external stakeholders perceive challenges because the school did not conduct simulation activities among school personnel, with a weighted mean score of 2.88. This implies that external stakeholders also find the absence of simulation activities challenging in preparing for the return to in-person classes.

Addressing the challenges related to shared responsibility in implementing post-pandemic in-person classes requires both internal and external stakeholders to collaborate. This involves proactive planning and community engagement to ensure a safe and successful return to in-person learning.

The successful reintroduction of in-person classes requires cooperation among internal and external parties through proactive planning and community involvement. Valdez (2020) emphasized the crucial role of management in ensuring accessible and well-maintained facilities and resources to enhance educational outcomes. Collaborating with stakeholders such as administrators, faculty, parents, local authorities, and healthcare professionals facilitates the development of comprehensive strategies for a safe return to classrooms. Continuous communication, resource management, and strategic planning are essential for addressing health protocols, classroom management, and academic support, fostering an environment conducive to learning and growth for all involved.

Table 1.1.2

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Work Arrangements

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3. There are no vaccinated teachers who will handle face-to-face classes in a safe learning environment to learners.	3.13	More Challenging	3.06	More Challenging
4. The school does not orient all its personnel on the work arrangement implemented during the face-to-face classes.	2.94	More Challenging	2.99	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.04	More Challenging	3.03	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Challenging (MC)

2.51 - 3.25 More Challenging (MRC)

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Challenging (MDC)

1.00 – 1.75 Less Challenging (LC)

The provided data focuses on the challenges encountered by both internal and external stakeholders in implementing face-to-face classes after the pandemic, specifically concerning work arrangements within school operations.

Both internal and external stakeholders have a grand weighted mean of around 3.04 and 3.03, respectively, indicating an overall perception of "More Challenging" conditions regarding work arrangements in the implementation of post-pandemic in-person classes. The standard deviations for both groups suggest moderate consistency in responses.

Indicator 3 indicates that internal stakeholders perceive more challenges related to the availability of vaccinated teachers for face-to-face classes, with a weighted mean score of 3.13. This suggests that internal stakeholders find it challenging to ensure there are enough vaccinated teachers to handle in-person classes safely. Indicator 4 highlights that internal stakeholders perceive challenges in orienting all school personnel regarding the work arrangements during face-to-face classes, with a weighted mean score of 2.94. This implies that internal stakeholders find it challenging to ensure all staff members are well-informed about the work arrangements in place.

External stakeholders, as indicated in Indicator 3, also perceive challenges regarding the availability of vaccinated teachers, with a weighted mean score of 3.06. This implies that external stakeholders share similar concerns about the availability of vaccinated teachers to ensure a safe learning environment. Indicator 4 shows that external stakeholders perceive more challenges in the orientation of school personnel regarding work arrangements, with a weighted mean score of 2.99. This suggests that external stakeholders also find it challenging to ensure all school staff are adequately oriented regarding work arrangements.

Therefore, to address the challenges faced by external stakeholders in securing vaccinated teachers and training school staff on work arrangements underscore the necessity for collaboration between internal and external stakeholders to address issues related to post-pandemic in-person instruction. Similarly, Akpabio (2019) emphasizes the significance of the physical environment in achieving educational goals, highlighting the importance of promoting teacher immunization, improving staff orientation, and fostering teamwork to ensure a safe learning environment. Coordinating efforts between internal and external stakeholders aligns with the recommendation to conduct thorough facility assessments to support educational objectives, as advocated by Akpabio. Together, these challenges can be overcome by educational institutions to establish secure, welcoming classrooms that prioritize both human and physical aspects of learning, facilitating effective post-pandemic education delivery.

Table 1.1.3*Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Classroom Layout and Structure*

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder	External Stakeholder	Internal Stakeholder	External Stakeholder
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
5. There is no limited number of seats to be occupied for the required number of maximum learners in the classroom.	3.11	More Challenging	3.05	More Challenging
6. The seats to be occupied do not have at least 1-2 meters apart.	3.03	More Challenging	2.81	More Challenging
7. The presence of markers and stickers on the floor to manage traffic system and physical distancing inside the classroom are not present.	2.91	More Challenging	2.98	More Challenging
8. In non-air-conditioned spaces, windows and doors are closed.	2.99	More Challenging	2.98	More Challenging
9. In air-conditioned spaces, there are no installed exhaust fans and HEPA filters guided by DOLE Department Order No.224-221 Guidelines on Ventilation for Workplaces and public Transport.	3.00	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
10. Regardless of the HVAC system, all classrooms have minimal number to no working electric fans except for schools with no electricity.	2.95	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.0	More Challenging	2.94	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Challenging (MC)

2.51 - 3.25 More Challenging (MRC)

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Challenging (MDC)

1.00 – 1.75 Less Challenging (LC)

Table 1.1.3 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic in managing school operations, focusing on classroom layout and structure.

Internal stakeholders find the lack of limited seating and inadequate spacing for maximum learners in classrooms to be more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.11. This indicates that they consider these issues significant obstacles that need immediate attention

and action. On the other hand, internal stakeholders rate the presence of markers and stickers for managing traffic and physical distancing in classrooms at a weighted mean score of 2.91. While still challenging, this score suggests that they perceive this issue as somewhat less critical compared to the limited seating and spacing concerns.

External stakeholders also find the lack of limited seating and inadequate spacing in classrooms to be very challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.05. This indicates that they share similar concerns with internal stakeholders regarding the classroom layout and structure. External stakeholders rate the absence of exhaust fans and HEPA filters

in air-conditioned spaces slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.90. While still challenging, this suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the limited seating and spacing challenges.

Both Internal Stakeholders (weighted mean: 3.0) and External Stakeholders (weighted mean: 2.94) face more challenging issues related to classroom layout and structure, including limited seating, inadequate spacing, and ventilation problems. Valenzuela and Bienvenido (2021) highlight the need for collaborative efforts among internal and external stakeholders in the education sector to address challenges in facility management. Internal stakeholders, such as school administrators and teachers, are responsible for optimizing classroom layouts, ensuring proper ventilation, and maintaining safety measures to enhance instructional delivery effectiveness. Meanwhile, external stakeholders, including government bodies and parents, must support these efforts through funding and policy advocacy. This collaboration is essential to improve maintenance practices, enhance managerial competencies, and create safer learning environments. Overall, collective action between internal and external stakeholders is crucial for overcoming facility management challenges and improving the quality of education delivery.

Table 1.1.4

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of School Traffic Management

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. There is no available temperature thermal scanner or thermal gun at the entrance and/or exit gates.	3.14	More Challenging	3.05	More Challenging
2. There is no available hand sanitizer or alcohol dispenser at school gates.	3.96	Most Challenging	4.00	Most Challenging
3. There is no available surgical masks at school entrance reserved for symptomatic individuals.	3.11	More Challenging	3.02	More Challenging
4. There is no display of school map at the entrance point indicating the location of the classrooms.	3.03	More Challenging	2.82	More Challenging
5. The school traffic management plan and strategies are not in place to ensure that physical distancing is observed.	2.91	More Challenging	3.04	More Challenging
6. The hallway ground markings for walking direction guide are not present.	2.99	More Challenging	3.01	More Challenging
7. There is no designation of spaces for queue in high traffic areas like restrooms, library, principal's office, etc.	3.14	More Challenging	3.02	More Challenging

8. There is no installation of signage's and/or ground markings in high traffic areas like restrooms and hand washing stations to ensure physical distancing.	2.94	More Challenging	2.95	More Challenging
9. For schools with visually impaired learners and personnel, signage's do not support Braille.	2.96	More Challenging	2.98	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.13	More Challenging	3.10	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*

1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*

1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.1.4 presents the challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, particularly in managing school operations concerning school traffic management.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of hand sanitizer or alcohol dispenser at school gates as most challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.96. This indicates that they consider this issue of utmost importance for maintaining safety. Internal stakeholders rate the availability of temperature thermal scanners at entrance/exit gates slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 3.14. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of hand sanitizers. However, external stakeholders also find the absence of hand sanitizer or alcohol dispenser at school gates to be most challenging, with a weighted mean score of 4.00. This implies that they share the same high level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this issue. External stakeholders rate the presence of markers and stickers for traffic management and physical distancing in classrooms slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.82. While still challenging, this suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical compared to the absence of hand sanitizers.

In this study, both internal (weighted mean: 3.13) and external (weighted mean: 3.10) stakeholders face challenges related to school traffic management, including the availability of temperature scanners, hand sanitizers, and proper signage.

The need for collaboration between internal and external stakeholders to improve traffic management parallels the recommendations made by Sakurai et al. (2019) according to her studies internal stakeholders are urged to implement safety measures, such as optimizing traffic flow within school premises, external stakeholders are encouraged to provide resources and guidance to enhance overall school safety. Sakurai et al. emphasize the importance of joint and sustainable efforts by various stakeholders to ensure comprehensive school safety, disaster management, and disaster education. This highlights the significance of collective action in addressing safety concerns within educational settings, where both internal and external stakeholders play vital roles in fostering a secure environment for students and staff.

Table 1.1.5

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Protective Measures, Hygiene Practices, and Safety Procedures

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The school has no established contact tracing procedures for all those who enter the school premises.	3.03	More Challenging	2.88	More Challenging
2. The school has not mobilized the school COVID-19 DRRM team to ensure effective implementation of the school's health and safety protocols that are in place and are observed during the preparation and progressive expansion of face-to-face classes.	3.01	More Challenging	3.09	More Challenging
3. There is no availability of surgical face mask.	3.12	More Challenging	3.14	More Challenging
4. There is no availability of antibacterial soap.	3.00	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
5. There is no availability of emergency health kits that include PPEs and other needed supplies and materials in the school clinic.	3.09	More Challenging	3.14	More Challenging
6. There is no availability of PPEs for COVID-19 team members, health personnel, maintenance, and security guards.	2.95	More Challenging	3.06	More Challenging
7. There is no availability of handwashing station/s with clean and safe water supply and antibacterial soap.	3.06	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
8. There is no availability of clean and safe toilet facilities.	2.96	More Challenging	3.10	More Challenging
9. There are no proper placements of handwashing facilities in strategic locations.	3.06	More Challenging	3.03	More Challenging
10. There are no proper placements of trash bins in strategic locations.	3.05	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
11. There are no displays of visual signages on proper waste management practices near trash bins (e.g. biodegradable, non-biodegradable, recyclable).	2.99	More Challenging	3.12	More Challenging
12. There are no displays of visual signages on proper handwashing in handwashing areas.	3.03	More Challenging	2.91	More Challenging
13. The school has not ensured regular sanitation and disinfection of school facilities, furniture, and equipment.	2.98	More Challenging	2.86	More Challenging
14. The school has no availability of a separate leak-proof trash bag/container with a cover properly labelled as "USED PPE" for disposal of all used PPE.	3.11	More Challenging	3.14	More Challenging
15. Collection of the leak-proof trash a day is not observed.	3.03	More Challenging	3.06	More Challenging
16. There is no availability of medical-grade face mask required for school personnel when collecting/handling the leak-proof trashbag/container.	3.01	More Challenging	2.86	More Challenging

17. There is no treatment through disinfection or spraying of the collected wastes with a chlorine solution.	2.96	More Challenging	3.10	More Challenging
18. There is no proper disposal of the disinfected PPEs with general waste to the final disposal facility.	2.96	More Challenging	3.10	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.02	More Challenging	3.02	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Challenging (**MC**)

2.51 - 3.25 More Challenging (**MRC**)

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Challenging (**MDC**)

1.00 – 1.75 Less Challenging (**LC**)

Table 1.1.5 presents the challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on managing school operations in terms of protective measures, hygiene practices, and safety procedures.

Internal stakeholders find the lack of surgical face masks available at school entrances for symptomatic individuals to be more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.12. This indicates that they perceive this issue as a top priority for safety. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of a separate leak-proof trash bag/container with a cover for used PPE disposal as more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.11. This score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the lack of surgical face masks.

Additionally, external stakeholders also find the lack of surgical face masks at school entrances for symptomatic individuals to be more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.14. This suggests that they share the same high level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this issue. External stakeholders rate the availability of antibacterial soap slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.90. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the lack of surgical face masks.

Internal stakeholders (weighted mean: 3.02) face challenges such as contact tracing, availability of hygiene supplies, and sanitation practices. External stakeholders (weighted mean: 3.02) perceive these challenges as more challenging.

This indicates that internal stakeholders, such as school administrators and teachers, must prioritize the implementation of hygiene practices and safety procedures outlined by the Ministry of Education (MoE, 2020) before schools can reopen. These measures include ensuring that all students and teachers wear face masks, maintaining a proper student-to-desk ratio, limiting the number of students per shift, maintaining physical distancing, and providing adequate supplies of sanitizer, cleaning water, and soap. External stakeholders, on the other hand, play a crucial role in supporting these efforts by ensuring the availability of necessary supplies and offering guidance on best practices to ensure compliance with the set standards. This collaborative approach between internal and external stakeholders is essential for creating a safe and healthy environment conducive to the reopening of schools.

Table 1.1.6*Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Communication Strategy*

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The school has no developed a communication plan.	3.00	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
2. There is no identification of platform of communication for coordination purposes among the learners, parents/guardians, and teachers.	3.09	More Challenging	3.10	More Challenging
3. There no database of contact number and address of parents/guardians of the learners is kept for easy retrieval of their contact details in case their child shows flu-like symptoms while in the school premises.	2.95	More Challenging	3.03	More Challenging
4. There is no posting of child-friendly Information, Education and Communication (IEC) materials on hygiene practices and respiratory etiquette including hand hygiene.	3.06	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
5. Orientation materials are not available for distribution to teachers, learners, parents, BLGU, DRRM team members, and persons-in-charge in ensuring observance of protocols.	2.96	More Challenging	3.12	More Challenging
6. The school has no proactive COVID-19 local hotline/help desk or any similar local mechanism that connects and coordinates to the hospitals, testing facilities, and LGUs.	3.06	More Challenging	2.91	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.02	More Challenging	2.99	More Challenging

Legend:3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.1.6. presents the challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on managing school operations in terms of communication strategy.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of a developed communication plan as more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.00. This indicates that they consider this issue a

top priority for effective communication. Additionally, internal stakeholders rate the absence of child-friendly Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials on hygiene practices

slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 3.06. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the lack of a communication plan. Meanwhile, external stakeholders also find the absence of a developed communication plan to be more challenging, with a weighted mean score of

2.90. This suggests that they share the same high level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of a proactive COVID-19 local hotline/help desk slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.91. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the lack of a communication plan.

Moreover, both internal (weighted mean: 3.02) and external (weighted mean: 2.99) stakeholders find communication strategy challenges to be challenging. Issues include the absence of a communication plan and contact databases.

It implies that effective communication is essential. Internal stakeholders must develop communication plans, and external stakeholders can assist by sharing information and facilitating communication between schools, parents, and local authorities. This suggests that effective communication is crucial in ensuring the successful implementation of transmission control measures in schools. Internal stakeholders, including school administrators and teachers, must develop comprehensive communication plans to disseminate information about safety protocols, updates, and guidelines to students, staff, and parents. External stakeholders can play a supportive role by sharing relevant information and facilitating communication channels between schools, parents, and local authorities.

As highlighted by Brandon et al. (2020), the continued implementation of transmission control measures, such as class size reduction, physical distancing, face masks, hand washing, temperature checks, and viral or antibody testing, is essential for maintaining a safe school environment. Clear and timely communication between internal and external stakeholders is necessary to ensure everyone remains informed and adheres to these measures effectively. This collaborative approach to communication is vital for minimizing the risk of COVID-19 transmission and maintaining the health and safety of all individuals within the school community.

Table 1.1.7

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Contingency Plan

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The school has not prepared a contingency plan for suspension or resumption of classes in case of COVID-19 resurgence in the community.	2.95	More Challenging	3.09	More Challenging
2. Distance learning modalities in the event of a class suspension due to COVID-19 resurgence is not included in the contingency plan.	3.06	More Challenging	2.98	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.01	More Challenging	3.04	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*

1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*

1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.1.7 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on managing school operations in terms of a contingency plan.

Internal stakeholders find the absence of a contingency plan for the suspension or resumption of classes in case of a COVID-19 resurgence to be more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.95. This indicates that they consider this issue of utmost importance

for preparedness. Internal stakeholders rate the inclusion of distance learning modalities in the contingency plan slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 3.06. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of a contingency plan. External stakeholders also find the absence of a contingency plan for suspension or resumption of classes to be more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.09. This implies that they share the same high level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this particular issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of distance learning modalities in the contingency plan slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.98. While still challenging, this suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of a contingency plan.

In the study, both internal (weighted mean: 3.01) and external (weighted mean: 3.04) stakeholders perceive challenges in preparing contingency plans for COVID-19 resurgence.

It implies that internal stakeholders should develop comprehensive contingency plans, including distance learning options. External stakeholders can provide guidance and resources to support these plans.

According to Karakose et al. (2022), in these circumstances, the proper implementation of COVID-19 protection protocols during learning and teaching in schools is of paramount importance, as school stakeholders play a key role in the continuation of teaching-learning throughout the epidemic and have undertaken essential responsibilities.

Table 1.2.1*Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Focusing on Teaching and Learning in Terms of Learning Resources*

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. There is no available Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) in the event of a class suspension due to COVID- 19 resurgence.	2.97	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
2. The school has not ensured that all teachers have the Teacher's Guide/Teachers' Manual on specific grade levels and learning areas that they are handling.	3.13	More Challenging	3.05	More Challenging
3. There is no available Weekly Learning Plan (WLP).	3.85	Most Challenging	3.69	Most Challenging
4. There is no available textbooks and other learning resources.	3.12	More Challenging	3.02	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.27	Most Challenging	3.17	Most Challenging

Legend:3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.2.1 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, specifically focusing on teaching and learning in terms of learning resources.

Internal stakeholders rate the absence of weekly learning plans (WLP) as most challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.85. This suggests that they consider the availability of WLPs crucial for effective teaching and learning. Internal stakeholders rate the availability of self-learning modules (SLMs) slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.97. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see the absence of SLMs as somewhat less critical compared to the lack of WLPs. External stakeholders also find the absence of weekly learning plans (WLP) most challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.69. This implies that they share the same high level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this particular issue. External stakeholders rate the availability of self-learning modules (SLMs) slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.90. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see the absence of SLMs as somewhat less critical than the lack of WLPs.

The absence of critical learning resources such as weekly learning plans, self-learning modules, teacher's guides, and textbooks poses significant challenges for both internal and external stakeholders. To address this, schools should prioritize the development and distribution of these resources to ensure that teaching and learning can continue seamlessly, even in the event of disruptions like COVID-19 resurgence.

Due to the pandemic, teachers shared as many materials as possible and expected students to choose the best materials for themselves, which caused many

challenges for students. Amita (2020) stated that learners encountered difficulties in choosing the best source amongst many sent by their teachers, affecting their academic performance and increasing their anxiety and frustration.

In the study of Agayon et al. (2021), they found out that teachers are greatly challenged in terms of learning' quality transfer, module distribution and retrieval, students' difficulties in following instruction, power disruption, internet connection, and health risks posed by the pandemic.

Table 1.2.2

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Focusing on Teaching and Learning in Terms of Face-to-Face Classes

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The arrival, breaks, and dismissal time are not staggered to avoid crowding of learners in the school premises.	2.42	Moderately Challenging	2.59	More Challenging
2. The school has not developed a teaching schedule that follows the minimum contact time for teaching and learning.	2.33	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging
3. The school has not ensured that learning remediation/intervention is part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time.	2.36	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging
4. The school has not ensured that the class size in standard number of 40 and below.	2.37	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging
5. The school has not comprehensively profiled learners who participated in the progressive expansion of the face-to-face classes.	2.33	Moderately Challenging	2.59	More Challenging
Grand Mean	2.36	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Challenging (MC)

2.51 - 3.25 More Challenging (MRC)

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Challenging (MDC)

1.00 – 1.75 Less Challenging (LC)

Table 1.2.2 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on teaching and learning in terms of face-to-face classes.

Internal stakeholders perceive that the lack of staggered arrival, breaks, and dismissal times, leading to crowded conditions in the school premises, is moderately challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.42. This suggests that they consider this

issue important for safety. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of learning remediation/intervention as part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.36. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than staggered arrival and dismissal times. External stakeholders also find the lack of staggered arrival, breaks, and dismissal times to avoid crowding of learners in the school premises more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.58. This implies that they share the same level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of clear procedure for referral systems for COVID-19 confirmed and suspected personnel and learners slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.58. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than staggered arrival and dismissal times.

It implies that staggering arrival, breaks, and dismissal times to avoid crowding and implementing remediation/intervention in the regular class schedule are seen as crucial safety measures. Schools need to focus on these areas to ensure a safe and effective return to face-to-face classes. Additionally, clear procedures for referral systems related to COVID-19 cases should be established to address health concerns promptly.

As a result of the research, school administrators revealed that technology leadership and crisis management skills are important needs in the pandemic process and that their competencies should be improved in these areas. In this context, characteristics and roles of good education, a good school, an ideal manager, and an ideal teacher would change after the pandemic. It is predicted that soon, digital learning shall become the main basis of education beyond support or an alternative to face-to-face learning.

The school heads must not only equip themselves with the knowledge of identifying these challenges, but they are expected to manage, capacitate, and empower the school personnel to make sure that equality and equity will be made possible. (DepEd Order No. 24 s.2020). Although this new normal setting in Education is crucial for school leaders, it will also allow them to test their management skills, specifically in making decisions. Having this situation, the school leaders need to consider alternative solutions to ensure that no child will be left behind and that Education will continue in this time of health crisis.

Table 1.2.3***Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Focusing on Teaching and Learning in Terms of Teacher’s Support***

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
10. There is no provision of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions to ensure the ability of teachers to deliver relevant teaching and learning strategies and ensure continuity of learning through a combination of distance learning and face-to-face classes.	2.54	More Challenging	2.21	Moderately Challenging
11. The school does not conduct coaching, mentoring, and training relevant in facilitating blended learning approach.	2.44	Moderately Challenging	2.18	Moderately Challenging
12. There is no orientation on the implementation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) included in their budget of work during the face-to-face classes.	2.49	Moderately Challenging	2.19	Moderately Challenging
13. There is no orientation on the observance of academic ease and provision of flexibility to learners in managing face-to-face classes.	2.51	More Challenging	2.21	Moderately Challenging
Grand Mean	2.50	Moderately Challenging	2.20	More Challenging

Legend:3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*2.51 - 3.25, *More Challenging (MRC)*1.76 – 2.50, *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*1.00 – 1.75, *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.2.3 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on teaching and learning in terms of teacher's support.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions as more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.54. This suggests that they consider these sessions important for teacher development and effective teaching. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of coaching, mentoring, and training relevant to facilitating a blended learning approach slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.44. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of LAC sessions. External stakeholders also find the absence of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.21. This implies that they share the same level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this particular issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of orientation on the implementation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.19. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of LAC sessions.

It implies that internal stakeholders emphasize the importance of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions for teacher development. Schools should prioritize the organization of these sessions to equip teachers with effective teaching and learning strategies. Additionally, coaching, mentoring, training, and orientation on relevant topics should be provided to enhance teacher preparedness.

Educators from all grades and contexts experienced the necessity of rethinking their roles, ways of supporting students' learning tasks (Rodríguez-Triana et al. 2020), and the image of students as self-organizing learners, active citizens, and autonomous social agents (Council of Europe 2016, 2018). This shift requires new learning, not only for students but especially for teachers. As Hollander (2021) intelligently remarks, 'the pandemic is taking higher education back to school.'

In 2018, Ezeugbor et al. conducted a study focusing on principals' staff personnel administrative strategies for fostering teacher job satisfaction. They discovered that principals must outsource funds internally or externally to provide teachers with a safe working atmosphere that allows them to demonstrate their best qualitative teaching.

Table 1.3.1

Challenges Encountered by the School Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Well-being and Protection in Terms of School Disinfection and Sanitation

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has not ensured that the available sanitation and disinfection materials are approved by the Philippine Food and Drug Administration (FDAI).	2.96	More Challenging	2.90	More Challenging
2.There is no availability of hand-sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in restrooms.	3.14	More Challenging	3.05	More Challenging
3.There is no availability of hand-sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in classroom.	3.59	Most Challenging	3.57	Most Challenging
4.There is no availability of disinfectant like hand-sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions in entrance/exit point.	3.11	More Challenging	3.02	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.20	Most Challenging	3.14	Most Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*

1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*

1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.3.1 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on well-being and protection in terms of school disinfection and sanitation.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in classrooms as most challenging, with a weighted mean

score of 3.59. This indicates that they consider this issue to be of utmost importance for maintaining hygiene. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in restrooms slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 3.14. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of these materials in classrooms. External stakeholders also find the absence of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in classrooms as most challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.57. This implies that they share the same high level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this particular issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in entrance/exit points slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 3.02. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of these materials in classrooms.

The provision of hand sanitizers, alcohol-based solutions, and disinfectants in classrooms and other school areas is vital for maintaining hygiene and preventing the spread of diseases like COVID-19. Schools must ensure the availability of these materials and maintain rigorous sanitation practices to protect the health of students and staff.

Bender, L. (2020) stated that schools should enforce regular hand washing with safe water and soap, alcohol rub/hand sanitizer, or chlorine solution at a minimum, daily disinfection, and cleaning of school surfaces.

Table 1.3.2

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Well-being and Protection in Terms of COVID-19 Case Management

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has not identified the strategies to detect COVID- 19 among the learners.	2.99	More Challenging	3.06	More Challenging
2.The school has not identified the strategies to isolate and manage learners with COVID- 19 symptoms	3.13	More Challenging	3.02	More Challenging
3.The school has not ensured availability and maintained the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counselling services to learners, teachers, and personnel for the entire school year.	3.11	More Challenging	3.19	More Challenging
4.The school has not established a clear procedure of referral system for COVID-19 confirmed and suspected personnel and learners.	3.10	More Challenging	3.22	More Challenging
5.The school has not established a clear contact tracing and quarantine system for close contacts of COVID- 19 confirmed positive cases.	2.97	More Challenging	3.10	More Challenging
Grand Mean	3.06	More Challenging	3.12	More Challenging

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00, *Most Challenging* 2.51 - 3.25, *More Challenging* 1.76 – 2.50, *Moderately Challenging* 1.00 – 1.75, *Less Challenging*

Table 1.3.2 presents the challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on well-being and protection in terms of COVID-19 case management.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of strategies to isolate and manage learners with COVID-19 symptoms as more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.13. This suggests that they consider this issue important for the safety and health of learners. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of a clear contact tracing and quarantine system for close contacts of COVID-19 confirmed positive cases slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.97. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of strategies for learners with symptoms. External stakeholders also find the absence of strategies to isolate and manage learners with COVID-19 symptoms more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.02. This implies that they share the same level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this particular issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of strategies to detect COVID-19 among learners slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 3.06. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of strategies for learners with symptoms.

It implies that the development of strategies to detect, isolate, manage COVID-19 cases, and provide mental health support is essential. Schools should establish clear procedures for referral and contact tracing systems, ensuring the safety and well-being of everyone within the school community.

In the same manner, well-being is also considered by the Department of Education in the implementation of face-to-face teaching as indicated in D.M. No. 30, s. 2022. It is adopted in the context of DepEd in all public secondary schools to protect the student's and teachers' well-being against COVID all over the country, which is consisted of indicators such as school disinfection, Sanitation, and COVID-19 Case Management, including most marginalized.

Table 1.3.3

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Well-being and Protection in Terms of Including the Most Marginalized

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has not established a mechanism in identifying learners who are most vulnerable and disadvantaged in terms of access to learning.	2.55	More Challenging	2.21	Moderately Challenging
2.The school has not developed learning strategies to cater the needs of the marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother- languages, and usage of Filipino Sign Language.	2.44	Moderately Challenging	2.18	Moderately Challenging
3.The school has not ensured participation in school-based services in which includes but is not limited to feeding and nutrition programs, immunizations, Mental Health and psychosocial Support, prevention of Violence against Children (VAC).	2.49	Moderately Challenging	2.19	Moderately Challenging
4.The school has not established close coordination with the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) Case Managers of those learners who are marginalized.	2.51	More Challenging	2.21	Moderately Challenging
Grand Mean	2.50	Moderately Challenging	2.20	Moderately Challenging

Legend:3.26 - 4.00 *Most Challenging (MC)*2.51 - 3.25 *More Challenging (MRC)*1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Challenging (MDC)*1.00 – 1.75 *Less Challenging (LC)*

Table 1.3.3 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on well-being and protection in terms of including the most marginalized.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of a mechanism for identifying learners who are most vulnerable and disadvantaged in terms of access to learning as more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.55. This suggests that they consider this issue important for equity in education. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of close coordination with the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) Case Managers of those learners who are marginalized slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.51. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the mechanism for identifying vulnerable learners. External stakeholders also find the absence of a mechanism for identifying vulnerable learners moderately challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.21. This implies that they share the same level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this particular issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of

learning strategies to cater to the needs of marginalized learners slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.18. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the mechanism for identifying vulnerable learners.

It implies that the development of strategies to detect, isolate, manage COVID-19 cases, and provide mental health support is essential. Schools should establish clear procedures for referral and contact tracing systems, ensuring the safety and well-being of everyone within the school community.

Brandon et al. (2020) underscore the critical importance of implementing transmission

control measures like class size reduction, physical distancing, and face masks to combat the spread of COVID-19 in educational settings. Despite these difficulties, teachers demonstrated resilience by employing coping techniques. As the situation is unlikely to improve soon, educators must remain adaptable, emphasizing continued adherence to safety measures and the provision of ongoing support to ensure the continuity of education.

Table 1.4

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Terms of School-Community Coordination

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has not developed a plan for the coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team TBHERT) in ensuring that protocols are observed properly.	2.45	Moderately Challenging	2.59	More Challenging
2.The school has not coordinated with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services, such as but not limited to deworming and weekly iron-folate acid supplementation.	2.38	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging
2. In collaboration with their local health offices, the school has no developed intensive health promotion campaign activities /support-policies to maintain optimal health seeking behaviors of learners and other community members.	2.41	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging
Grand Mean	2.41	Moderately Challenging	2.58	More Challenging

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Most Challenging 2.51 - 3.25, More Challenging 1.76 – 2.50, Moderately Challenging, 1.00 – 1.75, Less Challenging

Table 1.4 presents challenges encountered by internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on school-community coordination.

Internal stakeholders perceive the absence of a plan for coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) as moderately challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.45. This suggests that they consider this issue important for effective coordination. Internal stakeholders rate the absence of

coordination with respective local government units for routine school-based immunization and other school health-related services slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.38. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of a coordination plan with BLGU/BHERT. External stakeholders also find the absence of a plan for coordination with the BLGU/BHERT more challenging, with a weighted mean score of 2.59. This implies that they share the same level of concern as internal stakeholders regarding this issue. External stakeholders rate the absence of coordination with respective local government units for routine school-based immunization and other school health-related services slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.58. While still challenging, this score suggests that they see this issue as somewhat less critical than the absence of coordination with BLGU/BHERT.

Effective coordination with local government units, health teams, and community stakeholders is vital. Schools should develop clear plans for collaboration with entities like Barangay Local Government Units (BLGU) and Health Emergency Response Teams (BHERT) to ensure that health and safety protocols are properly observed. Coordination for school-based health services, including immunization and health promotion, is also necessary.

Coordination is the function of management that ensures that different departments and groups work in sync (Topper, 2017). Therefore, there is unity of action among the employees, groups, and departments. It also brings harmony in carrying out the different tasks and activities to efficiently achieve the organization's objectives. Coordination is an important aspect of any group effort. When an individual is working, there is no need for coordination. Therefore, the coordination function is an orderly arrangement of efforts providing unity of action to pursue a common goal. In an organization, all the departments must be part of a cohesive unit to optimize performance.

Part II. Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-face Classes After the Pandemic

Table 2.1.1*Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Shared Responsibility*

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has mobilized resources and support from community stakeholders to meet the standards of the health and safety protocols.	3.10	More Applied	3.09	More Applied
2. The school has conducted simulation activities among school personnel regarding protocols and routines to replicate and discuss possible scenarios during the actual conduct of face-to-face classes.	3.16	More Applied	3.12	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.13	More Applied	3.11	More Applied

Legend:3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied*2.51 - 3.25 *More Applied*1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Applied*1.00 – 1.75 *Less Applied*

Table 2.1.1 presents the coping strategies applied by both internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, specifically focusing on managing school operations in terms of Shared Responsibility.

"The school has conducted simulation activities among school personnel regarding protocols and routines" (weighted mean: 3.16). "The school has mobilized resources and support from community stakeholders to meet the standards of the health and safety protocols" (weighted mean: 3.09).

The weighted mean scores for both internal stakeholders (3.13) and external stakeholders (3.11) indicate a consensus among the stakeholders that the school has successfully mobilized resources and support from the community to meet health and safety standards.

With weighted mean scores above 3, this reflects a positive outlook, suggesting that shared responsibility is an opportunity that the school can capitalize on to ensure the smooth implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic. Internal stakeholders demonstrate strong support for simulation activities, indicating their confidence in preparedness. However, external stakeholders' slightly lower score regarding mobilizing community support suggests a potential need for better engagement and collaboration with the community to strengthen shared responsibility.

The school heads must not only equip themselves with the knowledge of identifying these challenges and opportunities, but they are expected to manage, capacitate, and empower the school personnel to ensure that equality and equity will be made possible (DepEd Order No. 24 s.2020).

Table 2.1.2

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in terms of Work Arrangements

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The number of teachers who will physically report meets the availability of vaccinated teachers who handle face-to-face classes in a safe learning environment to learners.	3.08	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
2.The school has oriented all its personnel on the work arrangement implemented during the face-to-face classes.	3.09	More Applied	3.00	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.09	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied (MA)*

2.51 - 3.25, *More Applied (MRA)*

1.76 – 2.50, *Moderately Applied (MDA)*

1.00- 1.75 *Less Applied (LA)*

Table 2.1.2 presents coping strategies applied by both internal and external stakeholders in managing school operations, specifically focusing on work arrangements.

"The school has oriented all its personnel on the work arrangement" (weighted mean: 3.09). "The number of teachers who will physically report meets the availability of vaccinated teachers who handle face-to-face classes" (weighted mean: 3.06).

The weighted mean scores for both internal stakeholders (3.09) and external stakeholders (3.03) are above 3, indicating agreement regarding the alignment of teachers' physical presence with vaccination status and personnel orientation. However, the slightly lower weighted mean score for external stakeholders suggests that there might be room for improvement in communication and training to ensure that all staff members fully understand and embrace the proposed work arrangements.

It implies that internal stakeholders show confidence in personnel orientation. The lower weighted mean score among external stakeholders highlights the importance of addressing concerns related to the number of vaccinated teachers, indicating a need for clearer communication and planning.

Table 2.1.3

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Classroom Layout and Structure

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The number of seats to be occupied must does not exceed the required number of maximum learners in the classroom.	3.07	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
2. Seats to be occupied have at least 1-2 meters apart.	3.09	More Applied	2.99	More Applied
3. There are presence of markers and stickers on the floor to manage traffic system and physical distancing inside the classroom.	3.09	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
4. In non-air-conditioned spaces, windows and doors are open.	3.10	More Applied	3.00	More Applied
5. In air-conditioned spaces, the school install exhaust fans and HEPA filters guided by DOLE Department Order No.224-221 Guidelines on Ventilation for Workplaces and public Transport.	3.11	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
5. Regardless of the HVAC system, all classrooms have working electric fans except for schools with no electricity.	3.10	More Applied	2.99	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.09	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Most Applied 2.51 - 3.25, More Applied 1.76 – 2.50, Moderately Applied 1.00 – 1.75, Less Applied

Table 2.1.3 presents coping strategies applied by both internal and external stakeholders in managing school operations, specifically focusing on classroom layout and structure. The indicator "In air-conditioned spaces, install exhaust fans and HEPA filters" received the highest weighted mean of 3.11 by internal stakeholders. Stakeholders generally agree on the importance of various classroom enhancements, as indicated by the weighted mean scores for both internal stakeholders (3.09) and external stakeholders (3.03).

However, there are specific concerns reflected in the slightly lower weighted mean scores for items related to the installation of exhaust fans and HEPA filters and maintaining adequate spacing between seats. Addressing these concerns through communication and possible adjustments is vital to ensure a safe and conducive classroom environment. Internal stakeholders support the installation of safety measures in air-conditioned spaces. External stakeholders' lower weighted mean score regarding seat spacing suggests the need for better explanation and assurance of safe classroom arrangements.

The study by Akpabio (2019) revealed that the physical environment is a major determinant in attaining the school's objectives; thus, school managers should conduct a comprehensive needs assessment of facilities

Table 2.1.4

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of School Traffic Management

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
11. The school has available temperature thermal scanner or thermal gun at the entrance and/or exit gates.	3.10	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
12. The school has available hand sanitizer or alcohol dispenser at gates.	3.10	More Applied	2.99	More Applied
12. The school has available surgical masks at school entrance reserved for symptomatic individuals.	3.08	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
13. The school has available display of school map at the entrance point indicating the location of the classrooms.	3.10	More Applied	3.02	More Applied
15. The school traffic management plan and strategies are in place to ensure that physical distancing is observed.	3.10	More Applied	3.04	More Applied
16. The hallway ground markings for walking direction guide are present.	3.09	More Applied	3.02	More Applied
17. There school has proper designation of spaces for queue in high traffic areas like restrooms, library, principal's office, etc.	3.09	More Applied	3.03	More Applied
18. The school has installation of signages and/or ground markings in high traffic areas like restrooms and handwashing stations to ensure physical distancing.	3.09	More Applied	3.02	More Applied
19. For schools with visually impaired learners and personnel, signages must be in Braille.	3.08	More Applied	3.02	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.09	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Applied (MA) 2.51 - 3.25, More Applied (MRA) 1.76 – 2.50, Moderately Applied (MDA) 1.00- 1.75 Less Applied (LA)

Table 2.1.4 presents the coping strategies applied by school stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, specifically focusing on managing school operations in terms of school traffic management.

The indicator "School traffic management plan and strategies are in place" received the highest weighted mean of 3.10, while the indicator "Availability of hand sanitizer or alcohol dispenser at school gates" obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.99.

The weighted mean scores for both internal stakeholders (3.09) and external stakeholders (3.03) suggest general support for the implementation of school traffic management measures.

However, there are concerns regarding the installation of signages in high-traffic areas, as indicated by the lower weighted mean scores. Effective communication and addressing these concerns will be essential for the smooth management of school traffic during face-to-face classes.

Giuseppina et al. (2020) found out that cleaning and disinfecting floors, surfaces, and all premises with alcohol or sanitizer should be done at least once per day with additional cleaning on frequently touched surfaces like door handles. He also stated that toilets must be cleaned frequently at least two or three times a day.

Table 2.1.5

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Protective Measures, Hygiene Practices, and Safety Procedures

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has established contact tracing procedures for all those who enter the school premises.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
2.The school has mobilized the school COVID-19 DRRM team to ensure effective implementation of the school's health and safety protocols that are in place and are observed during the preparation and progressive expansion of face-to-face classes.	3.08	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
3.There is availability of surgical face mask.	3.11	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
4.There is availability of antibacterial soap.	3.09	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
5.There is availability of emergency health kits that include PPEs and other needed supplies and materials in the school clinic.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
6.There is availability of PPEs for COVID-19 team members, health personnel, maintenance, and security guards.	3.08	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
7.There is available handwashing station/s with clean and safe water supply and antibacterial soap.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
8.There is availability of clean and safe toilet facilities.	3.09	More Applied	3.07	More Applied
9.There are placements of hand washing facilities in strategic locations.	3.11	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
10.There are placements of trash bins in strategic locations.	3.08	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
11.There are displays of visual sign ages on proper waste management practices near trash bins.	3.11	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
12.There are display of visual signages on proper hand washing in hand washing areas.	3.08	More Applied	3.07	More Applied
13.The school has ensured regular sanitation and disinfection of school facilities, furniture, and equipment.	3.12	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
14.The school has availability of a separate leak-proof trash bag/container with a cover properly labelled as "USED PPE" for disposal of all used PPE.	3.10	More Applied	3.06	More Applied

15.The school sets a collection of the leak-proof trash a day.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
16.There is the availability of medical-grade face mask required for school personnel when collecting trashbag/container.	3.09	More Applied	3.08	More Applied
17.There is treatment through disinfection or spraying of the collected wastes with a chlorine solution.	3.11	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
18.There is proper disposal of the disinfected PPEs with general waste to the final disposal facility.	3.09	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.10	More Applied	3.02	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Applied

2.51 - 3.25 More Applied

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Applied

1.00 – 1.75 Less Applied

Table 2.1.5 presents the coping strategies applied by school internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on managing school operations in terms of Protective Measures, Hygiene Practices, and Safety Procedures.

The grand weighted mean of 3.10 for internal stakeholders suggests a generally positive perception of the school's efforts in implementing COVID-19 safety measures. Internal stakeholders, including school staff, teachers, and administrators, view the school's initiatives such as regular sanitation, contact tracing, availability of hand washing stations, and emergency health kits positively. This indicates a high level of trust in the school's ability to provide a safe environment for both students and staff during face-to-face classes. The implication is that the school should maintain and further enhance these measures to ensure the ongoing safety of the school community. Additionally, continuous communication and feedback mechanisms with internal stakeholders can help address any specific concerns or areas for improvement.

The grand weighted mean of 3.02 for external stakeholders indicates that they also have a generally positive perception of the school's safety measures. External stakeholders, including parents, local authorities, and community members who interact with the school but are not part of its internal operations, recognize the school's efforts in areas such as the mobilization of teams, availability of antibacterial soap, and proper disposal practices. The implication here is that the school should maintain transparent communication with external stakeholders to keep them informed about safety measures and any changes in protocols. Collaborative efforts between the school and external stakeholders are essential to create a safe and supportive educational environment.

In summary, the grand weighted means suggest that both internal and external stakeholders perceive the school's COVID-19 safety measures positively, but there is always room for improvement and ongoing vigilance to ensure the safety and well-being of everyone

involved in the school community. Effective communication and continuous monitoring of these measures are crucial to maintain and enhance stakeholder trust and confidence.

The study conducted by Filomena et al. (2021) delved into the challenges faced in ensuring the continuity of teaching and learning in public higher education institutions in

the Philippines amidst and following the COVID-19 pandemic. This study resonates with the guidelines outlined by the Ministry of Education (MoE) in 2020 and the Werabe administrative town education office in 2020, which emphasize the necessity for schools to adhere to specific standards before resuming operations.

In accordance with these guidelines, schools are mandated to implement various safety measures to mitigate the spread of COVID-19 within educational settings. These measures include the compulsory wearing of face masks by both students and teachers, ensuring the allocation of one desk per student to maintain adequate physical distancing, limiting the number of students per shift to a maximum of 1000, enforcing a minimum 2-meter distance between staff and students within the school premises, and providing sufficient supplies of sanitizer, cleaning water, and soap tailored to the size of the student population.

The findings of Filomena et al. (2021) shed light on the practical challenges encountered by educational institutions in adhering to these standards while striving to sustain effective teaching and learning practices amidst the ongoing pandemic. The study underscores the importance of understanding and addressing these challenges to ensure the safety and well-being of students and staff, as well as the continuity of education during and beyond the pandemic era.

Table 2.1.6

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Communication Strategy

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has developed a communication plan.	3.08	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
2.There is identification of platform of communication for coordination purposes among the learners, parents/guardians, and teachers.	3.10	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
3.There is database of contact number and address of parents/guardians of the learners is kept for easy retrieval of their contact details in case their child shows flu-like symptoms while in the school premises.	3.09	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
4.There is posting of child-friendly Information, Education and Communication (IEC) materials on hygiene practices and respiratory etiquette including hand hygiene.	3.11	More Applied	3.07	More Applied
5.Orientation materials are made available for distribution to teachers, learners, parents, BLGU, DRRM team members, and persons-in-charge in ensuring observance of protocols.	3.08	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
6.The school has a proactive COVID-19 local hotline/help desk or any similar local mechanism that connects and coordinates to the hospitals, testing facilities, and LGUs.	3.09	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.09	More Applied	3.01	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied (MA)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Applied (MRA)*

1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Applied (MDA)*

1.00- 1.75 *Less Applied (LA)*

Table 2.1.6 presents the coping strategies applied by school stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on managing school operations in terms of Communication Strategy.

Internal stakeholders, including school staff, teachers, and administrators, perceive the school's communication strategy positively, with a grand weighted mean of 3.09. This indicates that internal stakeholders believe the school has taken significant steps to establish effective communication channels and plans. They recognize the development of a communication plan, the identification of communication platforms for coordination among learners, parents/guardians, and teachers, and the availability of contact information for quick response to health-related concerns. Additionally, the posting of child-friendly Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials and orientation materials for various stakeholders contributes to this positive perception. The presence of a proactive COVID-19 local hotline or help desk further demonstrates the school's commitment to clear and efficient communication during the pandemic. Overall, internal stakeholders view these communication strategies as coping strategies for effective coordination and information dissemination.

External stakeholders, such as parents, local authorities, and community members, also perceive the school's communication strategy positively, with a grand weighted mean of 3.01. This suggests that external stakeholders recognize the school's efforts in establishing communication channels and plans, albeit slightly lower than internal stakeholders. They acknowledge the identification of communication platforms and the availability of contact information for parents/guardians in case of flu-like symptoms in students. Furthermore, the posting of child-friendly IEC materials and orientation materials is seen as for effective communication. However, external stakeholders may perceive a lower level of proactive engagement through a COVID-19 local hotline or help desk compared to internal stakeholders.

These perceptions underscore the importance of effective communication strategies in managing school operations during and after the pandemic. For internal stakeholders, maintaining clear and consistent communication channels, orientation materials, and a proactive COVID-19 hotline will be crucial to sustain their positive perception and ensure efficient coordination within the school community. External stakeholders' recognition of these communication strategies signifies a level of trust, but the school should continue to improve and expand communication efforts to address their specific concerns and maintain transparency. Both internal and external stakeholders should be kept well-informed about safety protocols and any changes in the school's response to the ongoing COVID-19 situation to ensure a safe and cooperative educational environment.

DepEd Order No. 24 s.2020 mandates that school heads not only identify challenges but also manage, capacitate, and empower school personnel to ensure equality and equity in education. This aligns with research findings by Bruns, Filmer, and Patrinos (2020), which emphasize that involving multiple stakeholders enhances school

management. Collaboration between schools and community members is encouraged to facilitate school improvement, as highlighted in the study by Olguin and Keim (2019), which underscores the significance of active participation from students, parents, community members, and administrators in planning and executing various school processes. Thus, the involvement and empowerment of stakeholders, as emphasized by educational policies and supported by research, contribute to effective school management and improvement initiatives.

Table 2.1.7

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Managing School Operations in Terms of Contingency Plan

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Internal Stakeholder</i>		<i>External Stakeholder</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.The school has prepared a contingency plan for suspension or resumption of classes in case of COVID-19 resurgence in the community.	3.11	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
2.Distance learning modalities in the event of a class suspension due to COVID-19 resurgence is included in the contingency plan.	3.08	More Applied	3.07	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.10	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend:

- 3.26 - 4.00 Most Applied (MA)
- 2.51 - 3.25 More Applied (MRA)
- 1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Applied (MDA)
- 1.00- 1.75 Less Applied (LA)

Table 2.1.7 presents opportunities encountered by school stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, focusing on managing school operations in terms of the contingency plan.

Internal stakeholders, including school staff, teachers, and administrators, maintain a positive perception of the school's contingency plan, as indicated by the grand weighted mean of 3.10. They recognize the school's efforts in preparing a contingency plan for the suspension or resumption of classes in case of a COVID-19 resurgence in the community. Additionally, they appreciate the inclusion of distance learning modalities in the plan, ensuring that education can continue effectively in the event of class suspension. This positive perception suggests that internal stakeholders have confidence in the school's ability to adapt to changing circumstances and prioritize the continuation of education.

External stakeholders, which may include parents, local authorities, and community members, also hold a generally positive perception of the school's contingency plan, albeit slightly lower than internal stakeholders, with a grand weighted mean of 3.03. They acknowledge the school's preparedness for potential class

suspension or resumption due to COVID-19 resurgence and the inclusion of distance learning modalities. External stakeholders recognize that the school has considered alternative education methods to ensure that students' learning experiences are not disrupted in the face of challenges. This positive perception indicates that external stakeholders trust the school's commitment to providing education even in uncertain times.

Both internal and external stakeholders perceive the school's contingency plan positively, indicating that the school has taken proactive steps to address potential disruptions caused by COVID-19 resurgences. For internal stakeholders, the positive perception underscores the importance of maintaining and regularly updating the contingency plan.

Effective communication and training on the plan's implementation should be in place to ensure that everyone in the school community is well-prepared for potential challenges. External stakeholders' recognition of the contingency plan demonstrates a level of trust in the school's ability to adapt to changing circumstances. The school should continue to engage with external stakeholders, provide updates on the plan's execution, and seek their input to build stronger partnerships. Both internal and external stakeholders should be kept informed about the contingency plan and the school's readiness to respond to any potential disruptions, reinforcing confidence in the school's ability to provide a safe and uninterrupted learning environment.

This result affirms the study of Bautista et al. (2021), where distance learning has become the sole modality of the teaching and learning process in the Philippines due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The study found out that the majority of the respondents received adequate support from their respective schools in terms of capacity building, technical and data privacy matters, systems of information dissemination, and online learning management.

Table 2.2.1

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Focusing on Teaching and Learning in Terms of Learning Resources

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. There is available Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) in the event of a class suspension due to COVID- 19 resurgence.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
2. The school has ensured that all teachers have the Teacher's Guide/Teachers' Manual on specific grade levels and learning areas that they are handling.	3.06	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
3. There is available Weekly Learning Plan (WLP).	3.11	More Applied	3.00	More Applied
4. There are available textbooks and other learning resources.	3.09	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.09	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Applied (MA)

2.51 - 3.25, More Applied (MRA)

1.76 – 2.50, Moderately Applied (MDA)
 1.00- 1.75 Less Applied (LA)

In Table 2.2.1, which focuses on Learning Resources, both internal and external stakeholders expressed their views on various aspects of educational preparedness for face-to-face classes. The highest-rated statement among internal stakeholders was "Availability of Weekly Learning Plan (WLP)" with a weighted mean score of 3.11, indicating a strong emphasis on structured planning for in-person learning. External stakeholders, on the other hand, prioritized "Availability of Textbooks and other Learning Resources" with a weighted mean score of 3.06, underscoring the importance of tangible learning materials. However, both groups rated "Availability of Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) in the event of a class suspension" the lowest, with weighted mean scores of 3.09 for internal stakeholders and 2.98 for external stakeholders, implying that more attention may be needed in this area.

The emphasis on Weekly Learning Plans (WLP) underscores the importance of structured planning for in-person learning, highlighting the necessity of comprehensive plans to guide both teachers and students. Pentang (2021) reinforces this, emphasizing the need for teachers to employ current pedagogy for effective lesson delivery. Despite pandemic challenges, teachers support students through module creation, as noted by Malipot (2020).

However, Malipot also highlights issues like material costs and late printing demands. To address these challenges, schools should prioritize comprehensive weekly plans and ensure access to physical and digital resources for effective teaching and learning. This holistic approach integrates structured planning, pedagogical strategies, and resource accessibility, crucial for navigating the complexities of pandemic-era education.

Table 2.2.2

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Focusing on Teaching and Learning in Terms of Face-to-Face Classes

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
5. The arrival, breaks, and dismissal time are staggered to avoid crowding of learners in the school premises.	3.12	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
6. The school has developed a teaching schedule that follows the minimum contact time for teaching and learning.	3.06	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
7. The school has ensured that learning remediation/intervention is part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
8. The school has ensured that the class size in standard number of 40 and below.	3.06	More Applied	3.06	More Applied

9.The school has comprehensively profiled learners who participated in the progressive expansion of the face-to-face classes.	3.11	More Applied	2.99	More Applied
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Grand Mean	3.09	More Applied	3.01	More Applied
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Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Applied (MA)

2.51 - 3.25 More Applied (MRA)

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Applied (MDA)

1.00- 1.75 Less Applied (LA)

In Table 2.2.2, concerning Face-to-Face Classes, stakeholders assessed various operational aspects. Internal stakeholders highlighted "Arrival, breaks, and dismissal time are staggered" as crucial, with a weighted mean score of 3.12, indicating the importance of crowd control measures. External stakeholders, with a weighted mean score of 3.03, found "The school has developed a teaching schedule" as a key consideration. However, both groups placed lower importance on "The school has ensured that the class size is standard," which received weighted mean scores of 3.10 and 2.98, respectively, suggesting a need for more attention to class size management.

Stakeholders recognize the significance of crowd control measures, staggered schedules, and optimized class sizes to ensure the safety of students and staff during face-to-face classes. Schools should prioritize these aspects to minimize the risk of virus transmission. As guided by DM. No. 30, s. (2022), The learners' engagement in the teaching-learning process needs to be considered in the context of the face-to-face teaching and learning process. Designing and developing productive learning experiences exposes learners to most learning opportunities.

Table 2.2.3

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Focusing on Teaching and Learning in Terms of Teacher's Support

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
10. The school has the Provision of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions to ensure the ability of teachers to deliver relevant teaching and learning strategies and ensure continuity of learning through a combination of distance learning and face-to-face classes.	3.10	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
11. The school has conduct coaching, mentoring, and relevant training in facilitating blended learning approach.	3.15	More Applied	2.99	More Applied

12. The school has conducted an orientation on the implementation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) included in their budget of work during the face-to-face classes.	3.08	More Applied	3.07	More Applied
13. The school has conducted an orientation on the observance of academic ease and provision of flexibility to learners in managing face-to-face classes.	3.14	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.12	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied (MA)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Applied (MRA)*

1.76 - 2.50 *Moderately Applied (MDA)*

1.00- 1.75 *Less Applied (LA)*

Table 2.2.3 addresses teacher's support, with internal stakeholders assigning the highest rating to "Coaching, mentoring, and training relevant in facilitating a blended learning approach," earning a weighted mean score of 3.15. This underscores the significance of teacher development. External stakeholders also prioritize professional development but assign slightly lower importance, with a weighted mean score of 3.03 for "Provision of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions." Meanwhile, both groups perceive "Orientation on the observance of academic ease and provision of flexibility to learners" as less critical, with weighted mean scores of 3.14 for internal stakeholders and 2.98 for external stakeholders.

The emphasis on coaching, mentoring, and training for teachers, especially in facilitating blended learning, signifies the importance of ongoing professional development. This highlights the need for investment in training programs to equip teachers with skills for effective hybrid teaching methods, ensuring they can adapt to evolving educational needs. Additionally, balancing academic rigor with learners' well-being is crucial for both internal and external stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of flexibility and academic ease.

This focus on teacher development aligns with the findings of Makore and Shukuru (2019), who emphasized that investing in teachers is key to improving education quality. They highlighted the pivotal role of a skilled teaching force in ensuring quality education within the education system.

Moreover, Swaleha (2018) concluded that sustaining teachers' interest and commitment requires proper information, motivation, and supervision. This underscores the importance of providing teachers with support and guidance to maintain their enthusiasm and dedication to their roles and responsibilities. Therefore, investing in teacher development and support systems is essential for enhancing education quality and fostering a positive learning environment.

Table 2.3.1

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Well-Being Protection in Terms of School Disinfection and Sanitation

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder Weighted Mean	Stakeholder Verbal Interpretation	External Stakeholder Weighted Mean	Stakeholder Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has ensured that the available sanitation and disinfection materials are approved by the Philippine Food and Drug Administration (FDAI).	3.08	More Applied	3.12	More Applied
2.There is available of hand-sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in restrooms.	3.17	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
3.There is available hand-sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in classroom.	3.08	More Applied	3.07	More Applied
4.There is available disinfectant or hand-sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other in entrance /exit point.	3.14	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.12	More Applied	3.04	More Applied

Legend:3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied (MA)*2.51 - 3.25 *More Applied (MRA)*1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Applied (MDA)*1.00- 1.75 *Less Applied (LA)*

Table 2.3.1 centers on School Disinfection and Sanitation. Internal stakeholders underscored the importance of "Availability of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in restrooms" with a weighted mean score of 3.17, emphasizing the need for hygiene measures. External stakeholders assigned greater importance to "The school has ensured that the available sanitation and disinfection materials are approved by the Philippine Food and Drug Administration (FDA)," earning a weighted mean score of 3.12. However, both groups rated "Availability of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in the classroom" and "Availability of hand sanitizers/alcohol-based solutions/other disinfectants in the entrance/exit point" lower, with weighted mean scores ranging from 2.98 to 3.08, indicating room for improvement in these areas.

The emphasis on sanitation and hygiene measures is evident, focusing on ensuring approved disinfectants, especially in restrooms. Schools should maintain rigorous sanitation

protocols, ensuring the ready availability of alcohol-based solutions. Additionally, enhancing the availability of these materials in classrooms and entrance/exit points is essential for maintaining a safe learning environment.

Furthermore, Claire and Lindsay (2020) suggested that, in addition to requiring mask use and body temperature monitoring with a mobile app or the use of a contactless thermometer at school entrances, schools in Taiwan and Hong Kong should also be mandated to use plastic barriers in classrooms to increase student separation.

Table 2.3.2

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Well – being Protection in Terms of COVID-19 Case Management

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has identified strategies to detect COVID- 19 among the learners.	3.10	More Applied	3.13	More Applied
2.The school has identified strategies to isolate and manage learners with COVID- 19 symptoms.	3.13	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
3.The school has ensured availability and maintained the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counselling services to learners, teachers, and personnel for the entire school year.	3.13	More Applied	3.08	More Applied
4.The school has established a clear procedure of referral system for COVID-19 confirmed and suspected personnel and learners.	3.10	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
5. The school has established a clear contact tracing and quarantine system for close contacts of COVID- 19 confirmed positive cases.	3.14	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.12	More Applied	3.05	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied (MA)*

2.51 - 3.25 *More Applied (MRA)*

1.76 – 2.50 *Moderately Applied (MDA)*

1.00- 1.75 *Less Applied (LA)*

Table 2.3.2 addresses COVID-19 Case Management, both internal and external stakeholders agreed on the significance of "The school has established a clear contact tracing and quarantine system," with weighted mean scores of 3.14 and 3.06, respectively. These scores indicate a strong emphasis on preparedness for potential COVID-19 cases. However, they rated "The school has identified strategies to isolate and manage learners with COVID-19 symptoms" lower, with weighted mean scores of 3.13 for internal stakeholders and 2.98 for external stakeholders, suggesting the need for more robust protocols in this area.

Both internal and external stakeholders prioritize the establishment of clear contact tracing and quarantine systems, highlighting the need for schools to have robust protocols in place to respond promptly to potential COVID-19 cases. Strategies for isolating and managing learners with symptoms should be strengthened to ensure the safety of the school community.

Principals and educational personnel are encouraged to implement strategies, such as establishing routines, fostering good communication, and providing student support, to strengthen and restore a learning environment that may be considered "wounded" (Halladay Goldman et al., 2020).

Table 2.3.3

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in Well – being Protection in Terms of Including the Most Marginalized

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has established a mechanism in identifying learners who are most vulnerable and disadvantaged in terms of access to learning.	3.13	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
2.The school has developed learning strategies to cater the needs of the marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother- languages, and usage of Filipino Sign Language.	3.14	More Applied	3.08	More Applied
3.The school has ensured participation in school-based services in which includes but is not limited to feeding and nutrition programs, immunizations, Mental Health and psychosocial Support, prevention of Violence against Children (VAC).	3.13	More Applied	2.98	More Applied
4.The school has established close coordination with the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) Case Managers of those learners who are marginalized.	3.12	More Applied	3.06	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.13	More Applied	3.03	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 *Most Applied (MA)* 2.51 - 3.25, *More Applied (MRA)* 1.76 – 2.50, *Moderately Applied (MDA)* 1.00- 1.75 *Less Applied (LA)*

Table 2.3.3 illustrates the significance of addressing the needs of the most marginalized, as seen in the item "The school has developed learning strategies to cater to the needs of marginalized learners," with weighted mean scores of 3.14 for internal stakeholders and 3.08 for external stakeholders. However, both groups somewhat downplayed the importance of "The school has established a mechanism for identifying learners who are most vulnerable and

disadvantaged," with weighted mean scores of 3.13 and 2.98, respectively. This underscores the need to further address the needs of vulnerable students.

Stakeholders recognize the importance of addressing the needs of marginalized learners, including those with disabilities or vulnerabilities. Schools should continue developing inclusive learning strategies and mechanisms for identifying and supporting these students. This includes providing materials in accessible formats, such as Braille or sign language, and collaborating with external agencies to offer essential services.

Similarly, the Department of Education considers well-being in the implementation of face-to-face teaching, as indicated in D.M. No. 30, s. 2022. This directive is adopted throughout all public secondary schools in the context of DepEd, aiming to protect the well-being of students and teachers nationwide against COVID-19. It includes indicators such as school disinfection, sanitation, and COVID-19 case management, as well as addressing the needs of the most marginalized.

The teaching and learning process takes on a different shape in times of crisis. When disasters and crises, whether artificial or natural, occur, schools must be resilient and find new ways to continue teaching and learning activities (Chang-Richards et al., 2013).

Table 2.4

Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic in terms of School-Community Coordination

<i>Indicators</i>	Internal Stakeholder		External Stakeholder	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school has developed a plan for the coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (TBHERT) in ensuring that protocols are observed properly.	3.13	More Applied	2.97	More Applied
2. The school has coordinated with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services, such as but not limited to deworming and weekly iron-folate acid supplementation.	3.15	More Applied	3.10	More Applied
3.In collaboration with their local health offices, the school has developed intensive health promotion campaign activities /support-policies to maintain optimal health seeking behaviors of learners and other community members.	3.13	More Applied	2.96	More Applied
Grand Mean	3.14	More Applied	3.01	More Applied

Legend:

3.26 - 4.00 Most Applied (MA)

2.51 - 3.25 More Applied (MRA)

1.76 – 2.50 Moderately Applied (MDA)

1.00- 1.75 Less Applied (LA)

In relation to Table 2.4 (School-Community Coordination), internal stakeholders emphasized the importance of "The school has coordinated with their respective local government units for school health-related services," earning a weighted mean score of 3.15. This underscores the significance of inter-agency collaboration. External stakeholders also prioritized coordination but rated "The school has developed a plan for coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU)" slightly lower, with a weighted mean score of 2.97. Nonetheless, both groups acknowledged the importance of collaboration and assigned higher ratings to these statements compared to other aspects in this table, which received weighted mean scores ranging from 2.96 to 3.13.

Inter-agency collaboration, especially concerning health-related services and coordination with local government units, is highly valued. Schools should strengthen partnerships with local authorities and health organizations to ensure the effective implementation of health protocols, immunization programs, and support services for learners.

Coordination, as a fundamental function of management, ensures that various departments and groups within an organization work harmoniously towards shared objectives. It fosters unity of action among employees and departments, facilitating efficient task execution and ultimately contributing to the achievement of organizational goals (Topper, 2019). Similarly, when families, schools, and community institutions collaborate and coordinate their efforts, they collectively benefit in various ways.

In the context of education, coordination among families, schools, and community institutions is crucial for fostering a supportive learning environment and enhancing educational outcomes. When these stakeholders align their goals and strategies, everyone stands to gain. Schools receive informed support from families and community members, enabling them to better cater to the needs of students and provide a holistic education experience (Nageswaran, 2018). Families, in turn, have increased opportunities to actively contribute to their children's education, leading to greater engagement and academic success. Additionally, communities benefit from having an educated and responsible workforce, which can positively impact economic growth and social development.

In essence, just as coordination within organizations leads to improved efficiency and goal achievement, coordination among families, schools, and community institutions in the realm of education fosters collaboration, resource-sharing, and collective success for the benefit of all stakeholders involved.

Part III. Significant Difference on the Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic

Table 3.

Significant Difference on the Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External

				t-test for Equality of Means									
				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Differen	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the		Remarks		
										Lower	Upper		
On shared Responsibility	Equal variances	5.508	0.019	1.586	362	0.114	0.0660	0.0416	-0.0158	0.1478	Not Significant		
	Equal variances			1.465	203	0.144	0.0660	0.0450	-0.0228	0.1548	Not Significant		
On Work Arrangement	Equal variances	3.159	0.076	0.251	362	0.802	0.0095	0.0377	-0.0646	0.0836	Not Significant		
	Equal variances			0.236	213	0.813	0.0095	0.0401	-0.0695	0.0885	Not Significant		
On Classroom Layout and Structure	Equal variances	0.016	0.899	1.732	362	0.084	0.0544	0.0314	-0.0074	0.1161	Not Significant		
	Equal variances			1.796	279	0.074	0.0544	0.0303	-0.0052	0.1139	Not Significant		
On School Traffic Management	Equal variances	3.373	0.067	2.331	362	0.020	0.0503	0.0216	0.0079	0.0928	Significant		
	Equal variances			2.277	236	0.024	0.0503	0.0221	0.0068	0.0939	Significant		
On Protective Measure, Hygiene Practices and Safety Procedures	Equal variances	0.541	0.463	1.829	362	0.068	0.0294	0.0161	-0.0022	0.0610	Not Significant		
	Equal variances not			1.843	257	0.066	0.0294	0.0160	-0.0020	0.0608	Not Significant		
On Communication Strategy	Equal variances	2.125	0.146	1.713	362	0.087	0.0332	0.0194	-0.0049	0.0712	Not Significant		
	Equal variances			1.669	234	0.096	0.0332	0.0199	-0.0060	0.0723	Not Significant		
On Contingency Plan	Equal variances	0.137	0.712	-3.266	362	0.001	-0.1458	0.0446	-0.2336	-0.0580	Significant		
	Equal variances			-3.556	316	0.000	-0.1458	0.0410	-0.2265	-0.0652	Significant		
On Learnig Resources	Equal variances	10.969	0.001	3.630	362	0.000	0.0986	0.0272	0.0452	0.1521	Significant		
	Equal variances			3.471	223	0.001	0.0986	0.0284	0.0426	0.1547	Significant		
In-person Classes	Equal variances	1.686	0.195	-2.640	362	0.009	-0.2265	0.0858	-0.3953	-0.0578	Significant		
	Equal variances			-2.512	220	0.013	-0.2265	0.0902	-0.4042	-0.0488	Significant		
Teacher's Support	Equal variances	23.942	0.000	3.663	362	0.000	0.2978	0.0813	0.1379	0.4577	Significant		
	Equal variances			3.409	207	0.001	0.2978	0.0874	0.1256	0.4700	Significant		
On School disinfection and Sanitation	Equal variances	3.816	0.052	2.108	362	0.036	0.0638	0.0303	0.0043	0.1233	Significant		
	Equal variances			2.050	233	0.041	0.0638	0.0311	0.0025	0.1251	Significant		
On Covid-19 Case Management	Equal variances	0.133	0.716	-2.505	362	0.013	-0.0573	0.0229	-0.1023	-0.0123	Significant		
	Equal variances			-2.491	248	0.013	-0.0573	0.0230	-0.1026	-0.0120	Significant		
On Including the Most Marginalized	variances assumed	24.293	0.000	3.665	362	0.000	0.2978	0.0813	0.1380	0.4576	Significant		
	Equal variances			3.410	207	0.001	0.2978	0.0873	0.1256	0.4700	Significant		
On School Community Coordination	Equal variances assumed	3.696	0.055	-2.058	362	0.040	-0.1738	0.0845	-0.3400	-0.0077	Not Significant		
	Equal variances			-1.941	215	0.054	-0.1738	0.0895	-0.3503	0.0027	Not Significant		

Stakeholders in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic

Table 3 presents significant differences between Internal and External Stakeholders regarding the challenges encountered.

The analysis of challenges faced by both internal and external stakeholders in various aspects of the school environment reveals noteworthy findings. Specifically, significant differences exist between these stakeholder groups in specific areas, including school traffic management ($p = 0.020$), contingency planning ($p < 0.001$), learning

resources ($p < 0.001$), in-person classes ($p = 0.009$), teacher's support ($p < 0.001$), school disinfection and sanitation ($p = 0.036$), Covid-19 case management ($p = 0.013$), and addressing the needs of the most marginalized ($p < 0.001$). These differences suggest that tailored strategies and interventions may be necessary to address the unique challenges faced by internal and external stakeholders in these domains.

Conversely, in areas such as shared responsibility, work arrangement, classroom layout and structure, communication strategy, and school community coordination, no significant differences were found. This indicates that both stakeholder groups perceive similar challenges in these aspects of the school environment. These insights can guide educational institutions in developing targeted solutions to enhance stakeholder satisfaction and overall school performance.

In essence, the analysis implies significant differences between internal and external stakeholders in several areas, necessitating different approaches and solutions to address the challenges faced by these stakeholder groups. However, in other areas such as shared responsibility, work arrangement, classroom layout and structure, communication strategy, and school community coordination, no significant differences were observed between the two stakeholder groups.

Part IV. Significant Difference on the Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic

Table 4.

Significant Difference on the Coping Strategies Applied by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Face-to-Face Classes After the Pandemic

				Equality of Means														
				t								df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Remarks
																Lower	Upper	
On shared Responsibility	Equal variances assumed	5.151	0.024	0.742	362	0.4583	0.0257	0.0346	-0.0424	0.0938	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			0.791	299.631	0.4295	0.0257	0.0325	-0.0382	0.0896	Not Significant							
On Work Arrangement	Equal variances assumed	9.249	0.003	1.516	362	0.1303	0.0538	0.0355	-0.0160	0.1235	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			1.590	287.020	0.1129	0.0538	0.0338	-0.0128	0.1203	Not Significant							
On Classroom Layout and Structure	Equal variances assumed	7.643	0.006	1.743	362	0.0821	0.0579	0.0332	-0.0074	0.1231	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			1.808	278.304	0.0717	0.0579	0.0320	-0.0052	0.1209	Not Significant							
On School Traffic Management	Equal variances assumed	5.554	0.019	1.902	362	0.0580	0.0637	0.0335	-0.0022	0.1295	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			1.938	265.190	0.0537	0.0637	0.0329	-0.0010	0.1284	Not Significant							
On Protective Measure, Hygiene Practices and Safety Procedures	Equal variances assumed	9.077	0.003	2.048	362	0.0413	0.0677	0.0331	0.0027	0.1328	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.127	279.492	0.0343	0.0677	0.0318	0.0050	0.1304	Not Significant							
On Communication Strategy	Equal variances assumed	14.074	0.000	2.188	362	0.0293	0.0731	0.0334	0.0074	0.1387	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.280	282.169	0.0233	0.0731	0.0320	0.0100	0.1361	Not Significant							
On Contingency Plan	Equal variances assumed	14.449	0.000	2.180	362	0.0299	0.0764	0.0351	0.0075	0.1454	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.296	290.441	0.0224	0.0764	0.0333	0.0109	0.1419	Not Significant							
On Learning Resources	Equal variances assumed	10.015	0.002	1.883	362	0.0606	0.0640	0.0340	-0.0029	0.1308	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			1.970	285.585	0.0498	0.0640	0.0325	0.0001	0.1278	Not Significant							
In-person Classes	Equal variances assumed	14.874	0.000	2.224	362	0.0268	0.0761	0.0342	0.0088	0.1433	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.353	293.873	0.0193	0.0761	0.0323	0.0124	0.1397	Not Significant							
Teacher Support	Equal variances assumed	17.930	0.000	2.645	362	0.0085	0.0892	0.0337	0.0229	0.1554	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.780	288.624	0.0058	0.0892	0.0321	0.0260	0.1523	Not Significant							
On School disinfection and Sanitation	Equal variances assumed	13.202	0.000	2.447	362	0.0149	0.0792	0.0324	0.0156	0.1429	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.519	272.657	0.0124	0.0792	0.0315	0.0173	0.1412	Not Significant							
On Covid-19 Case Management	Equal variances assumed	9.971	0.002	2.371	362	0.0183	0.0774	0.0327	0.0132	0.1417	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			2.416	265.458	0.0163	0.0774	0.0321	0.0143	0.1406	Not Significant							
On Including the Most Marginalized	Equal variances assumed	22.459	0.000	3.070	362	0.0023	0.1047	0.0341	0.0376	0.1717	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			3.230	289.758	0.0014	0.1047	0.0324	0.0409	0.1684	Not Significant							
On School Community Coordination	Equal variances assumed	41.568	0.000	3.676	362	0.0003	0.1273	0.0346	0.0592	0.1954	Not Significant							
	Equal variances not assumed			4.054	325.561	0.0001	0.1273	0.0314	0.0655	0.1890	Not Significant							

Table 4 presents the significant differences between internal and external stakeholders in coping strategies.

The analysis of coping strategies between internal and external stakeholders across various categories reveals interesting findings. The T-test for independent samples was utilized in each category to assess the homogeneity of variances between the two groups. Unequal variances were observed in some instances, indicating potential variability in responses. However, despite these variations, the T-tests for equality of weighted means consistently show no significant difference between internal and external stakeholders in coping strategies. These results imply that both internal and external stakeholders adopt similar coping mechanisms when faced with challenges associated with the examined categories. Whether it pertains to shared responsibility, work arrangements, classroom layout, or any other aspect, the coping strategies employed by these stakeholder groups do not differ significantly. This suggests a level of coherence in their responses and highlights the importance of collaboration and unity in addressing the challenges they face.

The implications of these findings are twofold. Firstly, they indicate that both internal and external stakeholders within the context being studied have a similar understanding and approach when coping with various challenges. This alignment in coping strategies suggests a level of consensus and shared goals, which can be beneficial for coordinated efforts in managing and mitigating the challenges at hand. Secondly, the presence of unequal variances in some categories, as identified by the T-test, highlights the importance of recognizing and addressing potential variations in stakeholder responses. While these variations may not lead to significant differences in coping strategies, they could point to specific areas that require more attention or tailored interventions. Therefore, stakeholders and decision-makers should remain attentive to these nuances to ensure a well-informed and targeted approach to addressing challenges and maintaining a harmonious working relationship between internal and external stakeholders.

Part V. School Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan

The results presented in the previous section have paved the way for the development of the School Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan. This proposed plan aims to address the challenges encountered by the internal and external stakeholders, providing a framework to guide schools in addressing learning gaps resulting from pandemic-related disruptions. School Learning Recovery and Continuity Plans are designed to reflect the specific contexts and situations of schools and community learning centers, guiding them to better respond to the learning needs of students. The plan's objective is to ensure the recovery of student learning loss exacerbated by the pandemic through resilient, responsive, and efficient governance, management, and systems.

The Proposed School Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan take into consideration the provisions stipulated in the National Learning Recovery Program. Complete details of the plan are appended in Appendix A.

Conclusions

The researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

1. Internal and external stakeholders perceive challenges in shared responsibility, work arrangements, classroom layout, school traffic management, protective measures, hygiene practices, safety procedures, and communication strategy. Contingency planning also presents challenges. Focusing on Teaching and Learning: learning resources, in-person classes, teacher's support, well-being and protection, school disinfection and sanitation, COVID-19 case management, and inclusion of marginalized students are viewed as challenging areas.
2. Both internal and external stakeholders see more challenging in shared responsibility, work arrangements, classroom layout, school traffic management, protective measures, hygiene practices, safety procedures, communication strategy, contingency planning, and focusing on teaching and learning. This highlights potential areas for improvement and innovation. Well-being and Protection: presents Challenges in school disinfection and sanitation, COVID-19 case management, inclusion of marginalized students, and school-community coordination.
3. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the challenges encountered by the internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic is rejected.
4. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the coping strategies applied by the internal and external stakeholders to address the challenges encountered in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic is accepted.
5. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher developed a comprehensive School Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan to address the specific needs identified. The first step would involve conducting thorough assessments to pinpoint learning gaps and areas where students require additional support. This assessment process should incorporate academic evaluations, surveys, and feedback from teachers, learners, and parents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. The findings reveal that managing school operations poses challenges for both internal and external stakeholders. Shared responsibility, work arrangements, classroom layout, school traffic management, protective measures, hygiene

practices, safety procedures, communication strategy, and contingency planning are identified as areas of concern. In focusing on Teaching and Learning, challenges are noted in learning resources, in-person classes, teacher's support, well-being and protection, school disinfection and sanitation, COVID-19 case management, and the inclusion of marginalized students. Consequently, it is recommended to improve communication strategies addressing challenges related to shared responsibility, work arrangements, and contingency planning. Establishing regular communication channels and feedback mechanisms is also advised.

2. Managing School Operations is perceived as challenges by both internal and external stakeholders in areas such as shared responsibility, work arrangements, classroom layout, school traffic management, protective measures, hygiene practices, safety procedures, communication strategy, contingency planning, and focusing on teaching and learning. Areas needing improvement and innovation include well-being and protection, particularly in school disinfection and sanitation, COVID-19 case management, inclusion of marginalized students, and school-community coordination. Recommendations include exploring innovative ways to enhance classroom layouts and school traffic management for improved efficiency and safety.
 3. Significant differences exist among school stakeholders in their perceptions of challenges, particularly in school traffic management, contingency planning, learning resources, in-person classes, teacher's support, school disinfection and sanitation, COVID-19 case management, and inclusion of marginalized students. Customized strategies are recommended to address these differences, tailoring communication and intervention plans to specific concerns.
 4. Variations in variances are observed, with no significant difference in coping strategies between internal and external stakeholders across various categories. This suggests a unified approach to facing challenges and underscores the importance of collaboration and unity in addressing shared concerns. Recommendations include encouraging collaboration, coordination, and unity among all stakeholders.
 5. Considering that this study is limited to the challenges encountered and coping strategies applied by the internal and external stakeholders to address the challenges encountered in the implementation of face-to-face classes after the pandemic, future researchers may study the effectiveness of these strategies.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher commits to respect the data privacy laws and other rules indicated in the data privacy agreement memorandum from the Department of Education. All contacts will also be established prior to the study's conduct. The health and safety of the stakeholders as respondents will be taken into account by effective contact with the local IATF and adherence to safe health standards. In addition, accurate data interpretation with total impartiality will be maintained in order to enhance the study's standard utilizing the confirmability approach or respondent validation via summary of results if they agree

with any of the likely emerging viewpoints. Finally, the researcher is liable for any issues that may occur about the participants, gathered data, or the integrity of the study.

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